

Teaching games through Competitive Tactical Cycles (CTC) framework

David Gutiérrez

University of Castilla-La Mancha

How to reference this article: Gutierrez, D. (2025). *Teaching games through competitive tactical cycles framework*. University of Castilla-La Mancha. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17625375>

Competitive Tactical Cycles (CTC) is a Game Based Approach¹ that structures the learning process through instructional cycles guided by a tactical map. Each cycle lasts between three and four sessions and focuses consecutively on two complementary tactical problems or principles and concludes with a competition session. Throughout the cycle, a reference game is used as the main learning activity. In addition, CTC incorporates elements of the Sport Education model to make the learning experience more motivating and meaningful while also contributing to efficient lesson organization and management.

Teaching and learning process structure: tactical cycles

Cycles are instructional units lasting between three and four sessions. Each cycle focuses on two complementary tactical problems or principles. For example, in an invasion games unit, the first session may address the offensive tactical problem of maintaining possession, followed by a second session focused on the complementary defensive problem of regaining possession. For net and wall games, we propose that the learning process is structured around tactical principles related to the sending phase and others related to the movement phase (Table 1; Gutiérrez and Segovia, 2025). Tactical principles related to sending and movement are grouped in the same cycle according to functional complementarity and progressive complexity. For example, within a cycle, the first session could focus on creating free space by moving the opponent, and the second on moving to the base position.

Table 1. Unit Plan – “Net and Wall Games”

Number of CTC / Reference Game	Lesson 1 Sending phase tactical principle	Lesson 2 Movement phase tactical principle	Lesson 3 Competition
1) Line Game	Search for free <u>space</u> : moving the opponent	Move to the <u>base position</u>	Line Game
2) Round net	Reduction of the trajectory <u>time</u>	Stay <u>ready</u>	Round net
3) Square Game	Reduce the opponent's ability to <u>read</u> your sending	Anticipate the return	Square Game
4) Two hands tennis / mini tennis	Take advantage of the <u>opponent's weaknesses</u> .	Opponent's <u>strengths</u>	Two hands tennis / mini tennis
5) Pickleball / Students' game	All of them	All of them	Pickleball / Students' game

Tactical map

The tactical map serves as a framework for identifying tactical problems or principles, within a sport and its core rules of action, functioning as a blueprint for instructional design. From this

¹ ... learner-centered teaching and coaching practice in which the modified games set the base and framework for developing thoughtful, creative, intelligent, and skilful players (TGfU SIG, 2021).

framework, key questions and focal points can be developed to generate effective prompts and guide student thinking. The combined use of the tactical map and Sport Education-based strategies also promotes collaborative learning among students. Table 2 shows a tactical map for a net and wall unit (Gutiérrez and Segovia, 2025).

Table 2. Net and wall games TACTICAL MAP

Tactical principle	Key information / Action principles
SENDING PHASE	
I. Search for free <u>space</u> : moving the opponent.	Did you look at the opponent before throwing? Where was your opponent? Make it hard for him/her to get it: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aim for free space • Open angles • Vary: left-right; front-behind; strong-loose
II. Reduction of the trajectory <u>time</u> (from where you throw/hit the ball until it bounces).	Safe throwing/hitting, but if you can, make it quick (less time to response for the opponent). How is it faster? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard • Short • Flat • Throwing-hitting technique: If hitting is allowed
III. Reduce the opponent's ability to <u>read</u> your sending.	Safe sending (throwing or hitting), but if you can, pretend you're going to send somewhere else and change the gesture at the end ("deceive"): feints.
IV. Take advantage of the <u>opponent's weaknesses</u> .	Look for opponent's weaknesses on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opponent's movements: how is your opponent situated? Is he/she covering one side more than the other? • Opponent's sending skills: how does your opponent catch/hit? Is one side more difficult for him/her than the other?
MOVEMENT PHASE	
I. Move to the <u>base position</u>	As soon as you send, find your base position depending on where your opponent will probably throw: center of the "window" of your opponent's next throw.
II. Stay <u>ready</u>	Adopt an alert position: legs flexed and active that allow you to be prepared and oriented.
III. <u>Anticipate</u> the return	Watch your opponent to guess where he/she is going to send. Watch out for feints!
IV. React to the <u>opponent's strengths</u>	Think about how your opponent is scoring and cover that section of your game.

Reference Game: modified by representation and exaggeration

Each cycle has a *reference modified game*, which may be purpose-designed or one that already exists within the PE games repertory. Reference games should meet the criteria of *modification by representation*, so, they should set a rich learning context while being highly playable. At the same time the reference game should facilitate the focus on the tactical problems of the cycle. In this sense, they also fulfill the pedagogical purpose of *modification by exaggeration*. Although the same general game form is maintained throughout the entire cycle, purposeful variations should be introduced to enhance player adaptability and ensure appropriate challenge levels for learners with diverse abilities.

Sport Education model elements: competition, teams, and captain role

Although CTC can be implemented within a full Sport Education season, its primary focus is on content learning. Therefore, to reduce teacher workload, it is recommended to include only those Sport Education features that most directly support the development of game performance and sport literacy. In this sense, affiliation through permanent teams (with fixed spaces and distinctive colours, at least on competition days) and a rotating captain role are mainly used to improve class organization and continuity, while competition sessions are included to enhance motivation, authenticity, and meaningful learning.

Reflection Strategies

Throughout the lessons, game practice should be combined with different reflection strategies to enhance students' understanding of tactical problems and core action rules. The teacher should refer to the tactical map when guiding these reflections, so that students have a clear reference for identifying and organizing key information. Additionally, the teacher may incorporate other reflection strategies such as questioning, micro-teaching, freeze-and-reconstruct, peer evaluation, and time-outs, among others. To maximize motor engagement time and ensure cognitive participation for all students, it is recommended that most reflection activities take place within teams. In this way, the teacher pauses only one team to guide the reflection process, while the others continue playing.

CTC can be applied to a specific sport or through a thematic approach:

- **CTC in Net and wall games. Thematic approach. *Full unit in open access:***
Gutierrez, D. & Segovia, Y. (2025b). *Teaching net and wall games through competitive tactical cycles*. University of Castilla-La Mancha.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/397927339_Teaching_net_and_wall_games_through_competitive_tactical_cycles
- **CTC in Pickleball.**
Gutiérrez, D., & Segovia, Y. (2025a). Pickleball: Application of Teaching Games for Understanding in Secondary Education (Spain). In C. Farias, S. Pill & L. Griffin (Eds.) *Game-based Approaches in Physical Education* (pp. 198-217). Routledge.

References

Gutiérrez, D., & Segovia, Y. (2025a). Pickleball: Application of Teaching Games for Understanding in Secondary Education (Spain). In C. Farias, S. Pill & L. Griffin (Eds.) *Game-based Approaches in Physical Education* (pp. 198-217). Routledge.

Gutierrez & Segovia, Y. (2025). Teaching net and wall games through competitive tactical cycles. University of Castilla-La Mancha <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17704206>

Teaching Games for Understanding Special Interest Group (TGfU SIG) (2021). *Game-Based Consensus Statement*. <http://www.tgfinfo.com/game-based-consensus-statement.html>